

Re-Evaluation of the Efficacy of First Line Regimen for Helicobacter Pylori – A Retrospective Single Centre Observational StudyKoushik Chakma¹, Arkadip Choudhury², Sonali Bhaumik³, NilpadhiniDebbarma⁴, Avik Chakraborty⁵¹Assistant Professor, Department of Medicine, TMC & DR BRAM Teaching Hospital, Tripura²Assistant Professor, Department of Medicine, TMC & DR BRAM Teaching Hospital, Tripura³Assistant Professor, Department of Medicine, TMC & DR BRAM Teaching Hospital, Tripura⁴Post Graduate Trainee, Department of Medicine, TMC & DR BRAM Teaching Hospital, Tripura⁵Professor, Department of Medicine, TMC & DR BRAM Teaching Hospital, Tripura

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Helicobacter pylori, often known as H. pylori, a gram negative, flagellate, helical bacterium is responsible for a persistent bacterial illness that affects more than 50% of people worldwide. Countries with lower per capita incomes appear to have higher rates of this illness. Like other bacterial illnesses, the elimination of refractory infections is impacted by the increasing prevalence of antibiotic resistance and ultimately impacts human health.

Aim: The main aim of this investigation was to reassess the effectiveness of the conventional triple therapy plan for H. pylori.

Materials & Methods: 330 individuals who tested positive for a H. pylori stomach infection through Rapid urease test (RUT) and/or Giemsa staining of gastric biopsy specimens without any history of PPI or antibiotic use in last two weeks were split into two treatment groups using a 50/50 randomization ratio. One group (Group LVX) consisted of members who were administered 500 mg of levofloxacin once daily, 1 g of amoxicillin twice daily, and 40 mg of esomeprazole twice a day for fourteen days while the other group (Group CLARI) consisted of members who received twice-daily doses of amoxicillin (1 g), clarithromycin (500 mg) and esomeprazole (40 mg) for the same duration. Following a period of six-week after the completion of the courses of therapy, each patient in both the groups had an endoscopy and RUT or biopsy to determine if the H. pylori infection had fully resolved.

Results: 330 individuals who tested positive for H. Pylori were included in the study and divided in two groups consisting of 165 each. The baseline characteristics of the patients included in the two groups were matched. Of the 330 patients initially included, a data of a total of 5 patients (3 in Group LVX and 2 in Group CLARI) were not found and could not be followed. 27 patients had recorded adverse effects and decided to terminate treatment. 298 individuals finally completed the treatment. The eradication rate of H. pylori in Group LVX was found to be 71.62% based on RUT or biopsy while 81% showed clinical improvement and 79% showed endoscopic improvement. On the other hand, 68.65% of patients in Group CLARI showed eradication based on RUT or biopsy, while 79% and 77% demonstrated a clinical and endoscopic improvement respectively.

Conclusion: Both Levofloxacin and Amoxicillin based triple therapy was found to equally effective; but both the regimens exhibit rates of eradication that are less than optimum and low efficacy in the groups we studied. In the future, research should concentrate on determining the elements that may affect the results of therapy and investigating alternate first-line regimens to enhance eradication rates.

Keywords: Helicobacter Pylori, worldwide, Refractory infections, RUT (Rapid Urease Test).First-line therapies, Levofloxacin, Amoxicillin, clarithromycin, PPI (Proton Pump Inhibitor).

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Introduction

Helicobacter pylori, often known as H. pylori, a gram negative, flagellate, helical bacterium is responsible for a persistent bacterial illness that affects more than 50% of people worldwide. Countries with lower per capita incomes appear to have

higher rates of this illness. The increasing incidence of antibiotic resistance makes the eradication of refractory infections more difficult than it is for other bacterial diseases. Long-term effects on human health result from this. Campylobacter, a bac-

terium initially isolated from the intestines, was renamed *Helicobacter pylori* when the later was discovered in gastric juice and subsequently cultivated in vivo by Marshall and Warren in 1982[1]. A majority of the chronic bacterial illnesses that affect billions of people globally are caused by *Helicobacter pylori*. The conditions most often brought on by an *H. pylori* infection include gastritis, gastric ulcers, duodenal ulcers, gastric cancer, and gastric mucosa-associated lymphoid tissue (MALT) lymphoma [3, 4].

In addition to other illnesses, *Helicobacter pylori* may cause stomach cancer. *H. pylori* infection is diagnosed using both endoscopic methods such as rapid urease test (RUT) or Geimsa staining of gastric biopsy specimens as well as non-endoscopic techniques, such as the fast urease test, histopathology, culture, 13 C or 14 C urea breath test and stool antigen test. Most individuals with symptoms and positive *H. pylori* test results should be treated according to guidelines using one of the suggested pharmaceutical regimens for the suggested amount of time. Eliminating the *H. pylori* infection ought to be the main objective. This will stop the spread of resistant strains, lower expenses, ease anxiety, and avoid the need for additional treatment. When selecting the empirical first-line therapy, it is important to take into account the patient's history of antibiotic exposure, any medication allergies, and the rates of resistance in the affected area. [5]. Refractory *H. pylori* infection is now defined as a test result that stays positive for at least four weeks after at least one round of first-line *H. pylori* medication has been completed, according to the current guidelines. The test's sensitivity might be affected if patients have not used proton pump inhibitors or antibiotics for four weeks after finishing *H. pylori* therapy [6]. Consequently, this research set out to reevaluate how well the standard triple therapy regimen works in treating *H. pylori*.

Materials & Methods

Retrospective observational study was conducted at the Department of Medicine of Tripura Medical College and Dr. BRAM teaching hospital, Agartala for the study's duration of three years from June 2021 to May 2024. A sample size of 330 patients was determined to be adequate for the study using current prevalence statistics of *H. pylori* infection nationwide. All patients diagnosed with acid peptic illness and found to have *Helicobacter pylori* infection after upper gastrointestinal endoscopy made up the study population. Patients who hadn't received bismuth, a proton pump inhibitor (PPI) or any antibiotic in the preceding two weeks for their illness, patients who had a complete record of their pre and post treatment clinical data, a thorough documentation of pre and post treatment

endoscopic findings and histopathological data and/or data on RUT results and having a minimum age of 16 were included in the study. Patients were not included in the trial if they could not finish at least ten days of the allotted fourteen days of triple-drug treatment. Individuals whose antibiotic regimens were not followed with an *H. pylori* test were also not included in the study.

Data on baseline clinical evaluation, endoscopic findings along with the test results for *H. Pylori* were collected. Of the 330 individuals included in the study, 165 individuals who had received a levofloxacin-based triple therapy (LVX) regimen comprising 500 mg of levofloxacin orally once daily (OD), 1 gram of amoxicillin orally twice a day (BID), and an oral proton pump inhibitor (PPI), Esomeprazole 40 mg twice a day were allotted to the LVX group, while another 165 patients who had received a triple therapy regimen including 500 mg of clarithromycin twice daily, 1 gram of amoxicillin twice daily, and 40 mg Esomeprazole twice daily were allotted to the CLARI group. The baseline characteristics of the patients included in the two groups were matched.

Following the completion of the two weeks therapy, patients in both groups had received a once daily maintenance PPI therapy for another two weeks following which they were followed off PPI, bismuth or any other antibiotic for a period of four weeks. Individuals who could successfully complete these 8 weeks of regimen were deemed qualified for the study and were called in for a second upper gastrointestinal endoscopy. Documented data on the clinical status, endoscopy findings and RUT and/or histopathology obtained during this second visit was collected and compared with the baseline clinical status, findings of the baseline endoscopy, RUT and/or histological tests to determine whether *H. pylori* had been eradicated. A combination of hematoxylin, eosin, and Giemsa was used to stain every biopsy sample for histopathological analysis. All these information came from the endoscopic registry and the patients themselves. In addition to the reasons for cessation, the documentation also included various adverse effects that were associated with both forms of triple treatment.

Statistical Analysis

Excel and SPSS 21.0 were used to analyze the input data. Microsoft Excel was used to generate graphs that illustrate the data. We used the mean plus or minus the standard deviation to summarize continuous variables. We used the unpaired t-test to examine how the independent variable correlated with the outcome variable. With a p-value of less than 0.05, statistical significance was established.

Results:

Chart 1:

H. pylori stomach infection was present in 330 patients documented by RUT or biopsy. 298 individuals completed the treatment, while 27 patients had adverse effects and decided to terminate treatment. A total of five individuals were lost in follow-up. Treatment groups were equivalent concerning gender, average age, and the adverse effects of the drugs, except for the rash, which was more prevalent in the group that received levofloxacin. The overall eradication rate was 70%. The eradication rate of H. pylori in Group LVX was found to be 71.62% based on RUT or biopsy while 81% showed clinical improvement and 79% showed endoscopic improvement. On the other hand, 68.65% of patients in Group CLARI showed eradication based on RUT or biopsy, while 79% and 77% demonstrated a clinical and endoscopic improvement respectively. Though the eradication rate in the LVX group was numerically more than the CLARI group, it was not found to be statistically significant. Clinical and endoscopic improvement in both the groups were almost same

Discussion:

In recent years, it has been demonstrated that the levofloxacin (LVX) based regimen can be used as an alternative agent to the clarithromycin (CLARI) based regimen. Numerous trials have also investigated the utilization of LVX as a first-line therapy. The eradication rates of LVX-based triple therapy have been reported to be between 72 and 96% [7].

It is intriguing that all these studies have been conducted outside of the United States, with the majority being conducted in a variety of countries [8].

The initial prospective trial to investigate the efficacy of LVX-based triple therapy as a first-line therapy for H. pylori management was conducted by another study [9]. They divided one hundred patients into two groups based on the use of Amoxicillin or tinidazole, as well as PPI and LVX. It was observed that both groups attained high eradication rates in the intention to treat analysis, with 92% and 90%, respectively. One additional study trial compared LVX therapy with standard triple therapy and discovered that the eradication rate was 87% with levofloxacin based triple therapy and 84% with standard triple therapy [10]. There have been no studies conducted in our region to date that have compared the efficacy of LVX-based triple therapy to the conventional clarithromycin based triple therapy specially taking in to account the rather rampant use of clarithromycin or other macrolides for the management of respiratory infections in this region.

However, the overall eradication rate of 70.21% and individual groups wise eradication rates of 71.62% and 68.65% with levofloxacin and clarithromycin based triple therapies respectively as has been demonstrated in our study falls far short of the expected 80% eradication rate with triple drug therapy regimen for H. pylori.

Table 1: Total study sample and gender distribution

Total Final Patients Recruited for The Study	Male	Female
282	149	133

Table 2: Side-effects observed in the study sample during the treatment

Side Effects of Triple Therapy Leading to Discontinuation	Amoxy+ Levo (Levo Group)	Amoxy+ Clari (Clari Group)	P Value
Number: 27 single or multiple side-effects	12	15	>0.05
Diarrhoea	10	13	>0.05
Nausea & vomiting	09	09	>0.05
Dizziness	06	05	>0.05
Loss of appetite	06	06	>0.05
Rash	04	04	>0.05
Weakness	04	03	>0.05

Table 3: Endoscopic Finding of 298 Patients, All H. Pylori +Ve

Findings	Number
Duodenal ulcer	46
Gastric ulcer	42
Gastritis	210
Duodenal ulcer + gastritis	236
Gastric ulcer + gastritis	221
Either duodenal or gastric ulcer with or without gastritis	298

Table 4: Patients undergoing 2nd endoscopy and H. pylori test: 282, LVX group: 148, Clari group: 134

Total Patient: 282	Eradication of H. Pylori: 198 Eradication Rate: 70.21%
LVX Group: 148	Eradication of H. Pylori: 106 Eradication Rate: 71.62%
Clari Group; 134	Eradication of H. Pylori: 92 Eradication Rate: 68.65%

Patients	H. Pylori Eradication	Clinical Improvement	Endoscopic Improvement	P Value
Total	70.21%	80%	78%	>0.05
Lvx Group	71.62%	81%	79%	>0.05
Clari Group	68.65%	79 %	77%	>0.05

Since the initial Maastricht conference, the standard triple antibiotic therapy, which comprises of clarithromycin, amoxicillin, and a proton pump inhibitor (PPI), has been implemented frequently worldwide [11-15]. The initially established standard of minimum 80% eradication rate has been challenging to achieve due to the escalating resistance of H. pylori infection to the clarithromycin-based regimen that is frequently employed [12-15]. Subsequent research have also demonstrated that the eradication rates have decreased to 71% to 60% in different areas [16, 17]. Consequently, it was advised to conduct clarithromycin sensitivity testing in populations with a suspected clarithromycin resistance prevalence of 15–20% [18, 19]. Our analysis showed that the efficacy of both treatment regimens significantly decreased probably of H. pylori eradication due to resistance to the antibiotics used in both regimens. The frequency of clarithromycin resistant H. pylori infections is highest in Asian countries, accounting for about 30% of cases worldwide. Global criticism is growing in the meantime. The World Health Organization has determined that the antibiotic clarithromycin is resistant against Helicobacter pylori. The interval [20, 21] may be used to

represent the range. Asia has a far greater frequency of levofloxacin resistance than Europe [22]. Because fluoroquinolones are used to treat UTIs and macrolides are used to treat upper respiratory infections, H. pylori resistance to amoxicillin is more prevalent in different countries [23,24]. This might be related to the fact that South America and Asia utilize antibiotics more frequently. Several variables, including the presence or absence of certain genes, may contribute to Helicobacter pylori's antibiotic resistance [25,26]. On the other hand, women are becoming more resistant to clarithromycin, whereas males are becoming more resistant to levofloxacin [26,27].

Furthermore, compared to older individuals, the incidence of clarithromycin resistance is more significant among younger demographics, such as children and young adults. The earlier results surprised us, especially when it came to levofloxacin. This has motivated us to seek better treatment options for our patients. In addition to being challenging to deal with, the H. pylori bacterium is difficult to investigate since we do not possess the requisite methods. Using the patient's medical data, we could establish the patient's level of drug adherence. Our

region does not have sufficient detailed medical records, so we cannot verify whether all patients have been exposed to macrolides or fluoroquinolones in the past. This exists in both hospital and clinic settings. Questioning patients was the sole method that could be used to investigate their drugs history, and this method was effective in cases when the antibiotics had been taken within two to three weeks before enrollment. Furthermore, in our region, as well as in other underdeveloped countries, there is a significant frequency of antibiotic abuse. This is further exacerbated by the fact that these pharmaceuticals are easily accessible from local pharmacies, even without a prescription from a physician.

Conclusion:

The efficiency of levofloxacin based triple drug regime in treating stomach *H. pylori* infection is numerically slightly more than clarithromycin-based regime, though it was not statistically significant; nonetheless, both regimens exhibit rates of eradication that are less than optimum and low efficacy in the groups we studied.

It is recommended that future studies concentrate on determining the elements that may affect the results of therapy and investigating alternate first-line regimens to enhance the eradication rate.

References:

1. Marshall B, Warren JR. Unidentified curved bacilli in the stomach of patients with gastritis and peptic ulceration. *The Lancet*. 1984 Jun 16;323(8390):1311-5.
2. Metwally MA, Abd El Hamid HS, Alegaily HS, Emara NM, Aish A, Elsayed EA, Abdelhamid MS. Relationship between Helicobacter Pylori Morphological Forms in Gastric Biopsy and Helicobacter Pylori Stool Antigen. *Benha Medical Journal*. 2024 May 1;41(2):56-65.
3. Lee ME, Katz PO. Gastroesophageal reflux disease and the Role of Helicobacter pylori. In *Esophageal Disease and the Role of the Microbiome* 2023 Jan 1 (pp. 61-76). Academic Press.
4. Fallone CA, Chiba N, van Zanten SV, Fischbach L, Gisbert JP, Hunt RH, Jones NL, Render C, Leontiadis GI, Moayyedi P, Marshall JK. The Toronto consensus for the treatment of Helicobacter pylori infection in adults. *Gastroenterology*. 2016 Jul 1;151(1):51-69.
5. Sugano K, Tack J, Kuipers EJ, Graham DY, El-Omar EM, Miura S, Haruma K, Asaka M, Uemura N, Malfertheiner P. Kyoto global consensus report on Helicobacter pylori gastritis. *Gut*. 2015 Sep 1;64(9):1353-67.
6. Fallone CA, Moss SF, Malfertheiner P. Reconciliation of recent Helicobacter pylori treatment guidelines in a time of increasing antibiotic resistance. *Gastroenterology*. 2019 Jul 1;157(1):44-53.
7. Nista EC, Candelli M, Zocco MA, Cremonini F, Ojetti V, Finizio R, Spada C, Cammarota G, Gasbarrini G, Gasbarrini A. Levofloxacin-based triple therapy in first-line treatment for Helicobacter pylori eradication. *Official journal of the American College of Gastroenterology | ACG*. 2006 Sep 1;101(9):1985-90.
8. Zullo A, Hassan C, De Francesco V, Lorenzetti R, Marignani M, Angeletti S, Ierardi EN, Morini S. A third-line levofloxacin-based rescue therapy for Helicobacter pylori eradication. *Digestive and liver disease*. 2003 Apr 1;35(4):232-6.
9. Wong BC, Wong WM, Yee YK, Hung WK, Yip AW, Szeto ML, Li KF, Lau P, Fung FM, Tong TS, Lai KC. Rabeprazole-based 3-day and 7-day triple therapy vs. omeprazole-based 7-day triple therapy for the treatment of Helicobacter pylori infection. *Alimentary pharmacology & therapeutics*. 2001 Dec 27;15(12):1959-65.
10. Bilardi C, Dulbecco P, Zentilin P, Reglioni S, Iiritano E, Parodi A, Accornero L, Savarino E, Mansi C, Mamone M, Vigneri S. A 10-day levofloxacin-based therapy in patients with resistant Helicobacter pylori infection: a controlled trial. *Clinical Gastroenterology and Hepatology*. 2004 Nov 1;2(11):997-1002.
11. Venerito M, Krieger T, Ecker T, Leandro G, Malfertheiner P. Meta-analysis of bismuth quadruple therapy versus clarithromycin triple therapy for empiric primary treatment of Helicobacter pylori infection. *Digestion*. 2013 Jul;88(1):33-45.
12. Gisbert JP, Calvet X, O'Connor A, Megraud F, O'Morain CA. Sequential therapy for Helicobacter pylori eradication: a critical review. *Journal of clinical gastroenterology*. 2010 May 1;44(5):313-25.
13. Graham DY, Fischbach L. Helicobacter pylori treatment in the era of increasing antibiotic resistance. *Gut*. 2010 Aug 1;59(8):1143-53.
14. Malfertheiner P, Megraud F, O'morain C, Hungin AP, Jones R, Axon A, Graham DY, Tytgat G, European Helicobacter Pylori Study Group (EHPSG). Current concepts in the management of Helicobacter pylori infection—The Maastricht 2-2000 Consensus Report. *Alimentary pharmacology & therapeutics*. 2002 Feb 20;16(2):167-80.
15. Chey WD, Leontiadis GI, Howden CW, Moss SF. ACG clinical guideline: treatment of Helicobacter pylori infection. *Official journal of the American College of Gastroenterology | ACG*. 2017 Feb 1;112(2):212-39.
16. Pnark JY, Dunbar KB, Mitui M, Arnold CA, Lam-Himlin DM, Valasek MA, Thung I, Okwara C, Coss E, Cryer B, Doern CD. Heli-

- cobacter pylori clarithromycin resistance and treatment failure are common in the USA. Digestive diseases and sciences. 2016 Aug; 61:2373-80.
17. Gumurdulu Y, Serin E, Özer B, Kayaselcuk F, Ozsahin K, Cosar AM, Gursoy M, Gur G, Yilmaz U, Boyacioglu S. Low eradication rate of Helicobacter pylori with triple 7-14 days and quadruple therapy in Turkey. World Journal of Gastroenterology. 2004 Mar 3;10(5):668.
 18. Shetty V, Lamichhane B, Tay CY, Pai GC, Lingadakai R, Balaraju G, Shetty S, Ballal M, Chua EG. High primary resistance to metronidazole and levofloxacin and moderate resistance to clarithromycin in Helicobacter pylori isolated from Karnataka patients. Gut pathogens. 2019 Dec; 11:1-8.
 19. Savoldi A, Carrara E, Graham DY, Conti M, Tacconelli E. Prevalence of antibiotic resistance in Helicobacter pylori: a systematic review and meta-analysis in World Health Organization regions. Gastroenterology. 2018 Nov 1;155(5):1372-82.
 20. Keikha M, Askari P, Ghazvini K, Karbalaei M. Levofloxacin-based therapy as an efficient alternative for eradicating Helicobacter pylori infection in Iran: a systematic review and meta-analysis. Journal of Global Antimicrobial Resistance. 2022 Jun 1; 29:420-9.
 21. Tariq H, Patel H, Kamal MU, Abbas N, Ameen M, Azam S, Kumar K, Ravi M, Vootla V, Shaikh D, Amanchi V. Reevaluation of the efficacy of first-line regimen for Helicobacter pylori. Clinical and Experimental Gastroenterology. 2020 Jan 22:25-33.
 22. Lim SG, Park RW, Shin SJ, Yoon D, Kang JK, Hwang JC, Kim SS, Kim JH, Lee KM. The relationship between the failure to eradicate Helicobacter pylori and previous antibiotics use. Digestive and Liver Disease. 2016 Apr 1;48(4):385-90.
 23. Provenzano A, Hospodar AR, Meyer AL, Leonardi Vinci D, Hwang EY, Butrus CM, Polidori P. Multidrug-resistant gram-negative organisms: a review of recently approved antibiotics and novel pipeline agents. International Journal of Clinical Pharmacy. 2020 Aug; 42:1016-25.
 24. De Francesco V, Giorgio F, Hassan C, Manes G, Vannella L, Panella C, Ierardi E, Zullo A. Worldwide H. pylori antibiotic resistance: a systematic. J Gastrointestin Liver Dis. 2010 Dec;19(4):409-14.
 25. Ahmed N, Sechi LA. Helicobacter pylori and gastroduodenal pathology: new threats of the old friend. Annals of clinical microbiology and antimicrobials. 2005 Dec; 4:1-0.
 26. González-Stegmaier R, Aguila-Torres P, Villaruel-Espíndola F. Historical and Molecular Perspectives on the Presence of Helicobacter pylori in Latin America: A Niche to Improve Gastric Cancer Risk Assessment. International Journal of Molecular Sciences. 2024 Feb 1;25(3):1761.
 27. Katelaris P, Hunt R, Bazzoli F, Cohen H, Fock KM, Gemilyan M, Malfertheiner P, Mégraud F, Piscocoya A, Quach D, Vakil N. Helicobacter pylori World Gastroenterology Organization Global Guideline. Journal of Clinical Gastroenterology. 2023 Feb 1; 57(2):111-26.